

TERRASAR-X / PAZ DATA IN STUDIES OF GLACIERS AND MOUNTAIN HAZARDS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Glaciers are sensitive indicators of climate change in Central Asia. This study applies TerraSAR-X and PAZ satellite data to investigate glacier surface changes, snow avalanche mapping, and landslide deformations in selected mountain areas of Uzbekistan. Radar remote sensing methods allow reliable observations in regions that are difficult to access for ground measurements. The results demonstrate the potential of high-resolution SAR data for monitoring glacier dynamics and hazardous processes. These findings may serve as a basis for future improvements in glacier mass change assessment, natural hazard evaluation, and adaptation planning in mountain regions of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *SAR data, innovation techniques, glaciers, snow cover, avalanches, landslides, Uzbekistan*

Introduction. Monitoring the state of glaciers and mountain hazards is a key task for both scientific research and practical applications in Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan, due to ongoing climate change in the region and the need to develop adaptation measures. In recent decades, the rapid progress of remote sensing technologies, especially synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite constellations, has created new opportunities for operational and comprehensive monitoring. Beyond mapping glacier area and morphology, these data provide valuable insights into dynamic parameters such as surface lowering rates, ice flow velocity, and long-term changes in glacier mass. Moreover, because radar systems can get useful information regardless of time of day or weather conditions, they enable the investigation of features that cannot be observed with optical imagery, such as snow wetness, as well as the identification of avalanche tracks and the determination of their genesis, which we attempted to implement in this study.

The potential synergies between the German TerraSAR-X/TanDEM-X (TSX/TDX) mission and the Spanish PAZ satellite are well known and have a wide range of applications. While bistatic TSX/TDX acquisitions can provide highly precise topographic information, combined TSX/TDX/PAZ data with short temporal and perpendicular baselines deliver valuable deformation measurements and enable the detection of small surface changes, even in vegetated areas [Alonso-González et al., 2021; Krieger et al., 2007]. This capability is particularly relevant in high-mountain environments, where access is limited and optical monitoring is often constrained by cloud cover, snow, or shadows.

The objective of this study was to examine the capabilities of TerraSAR-X and PAZ SAR data, using innovative methods and advanced processing techniques, for monitoring glaciers, snow cover, avalanches, and landslides in selected mountainous regions of Uzbekistan.

Since both platforms are almost identical and were launched in the same orbital plane, an acquisition plan was developed for the study sites, and comparable images of the same areas under the same geometry were regularly obtained from both systems. By combining the two missions, the individual revisit time of 11 days was effectively reduced to 4 and 7 days, allowing the observation of rapid surface changes that was previously inaccessible.

The study sites included:

- 1) the Pskem River basin, to assess glacier surface changes during August–October of 2022 and 2023;

- 2) the Kamchik Pass area, to identify snow distribution and avalanche tracks during January–April of 2022 and 2023;
- 3) the Akhangaran Reservoir area, to analyze surface deformation and detect active landslides during snow-free periods (March–June, 2022 and 2023).

The input data consisted of SLC-type X-band constellation datasets, acquired in both ascending and descending orbits. SM mode was applied to the glacier area, while SM-SL mode was used for the snow avalanche and landslide areas. In total, 29 dataset pairs were analyzed for the glacier area, 19 pairs for the avalanche area, and 15 pairs for the landslide area. Data processing was performed using ENVI+IDL software. Depending on the acquisition type and study site, the reference DEMs were either the Global TDM DEM or the AW3D DEM.

Methods. The study employed Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) techniques to analyze glacier and landslide surface deformation in selected mountain areas of Uzbekistan. DInSAR is based on phase differences between at least two complex SAR images acquired over the same area at different times, forming an interferometric pair [Ferretti et al., 2007]. The interferometric phase contains several components, including topographic, orbital, atmospheric, and deformation signals. To isolate the displacement signal, the topographic phase contribution was removed using reference DEMs.

Since the study sites differ in altitude, topographic complexity, and climatic conditions, different processing algorithms were explored. For deformation monitoring, the interferometric chain included filtering of the interferograms using the Goldstein method, phase unwrapping based on the Minimum Cost Flow algorithm. The phase refinement and re-flattening corrections were applied for several pairs. These procedures were essential to reduce noise and improve the reliability of phase measurements, particularly in areas with steep terrain or low coherence.

For avalanche monitoring, methods based on radar signal coherence and intensity change detection were applied. The coherence between two SAR acquisitions reflects the similarity of scatterers and is sensitive to surface changes such as snow avalanches. By analyzing coherence loss and intensity variations over short temporal baselines (4 days), avalanche release zones and flow tracks could be identified. RGB composites of intensity and coherence changes were generated, providing a visual tool for distinguishing avalanche tracks from other types of surface changes. These methods complement existing hazard mapping approaches and allow short-term hazard monitoring in regions where field surveys are difficult or dangerous.

Results and Discussions. TSX/PAZ data with DInSAR techniques enabled estimation of daily glacier surface lowering rates, in contrast to TSX/TDX data for different years and InSAR techniques, which provides annual elevation changes. Despite suboptimal TSX/TDX coverage for the Pskem River basin, the mean annual mass balance of the Barkrak Glacier ablation area was -0.82 ± 0.36 m w.e. (2000–2012) [Semakova & Bühler, 2017], and during drought years 2012–2014, the elevation changes for 10 glaciers averaged -0.68 m/year (-1.08 m w.e.).

Deformation precision depended on coherence, influenced by meteorological conditions and glacier dynamics. Positive vertical displacements were observed on upper-basin glaciers in late October, while negative values predominated in August. On unstable surfaces, radar decorrelation occurred. Using high-coherence scenes, the Barkrak Glacier's daily lowering rate was ~ 2 mm/day (August–October 2023).

Comparison of the results with precipitation data from the Oygaining station or ERA-5 reanalysis was unreliable due to orographic effects and modeling uncertainties, highlighting the need for high-precision DGPS data for validation. For landslide area, satellite-derived vertical displacements agreed acceptably with ground measurements [Семакова и др., 2024]. Installation of a corner reflector near the Barkrak Glacier will improve calibration for unstable surfaces.

TSX/PAZ datasets were also used to estimate ice velocity and avalanche feeding, which is an important component of mass balance for small Western Tien-Shan glaciers. Avalanche

feeding was assessed using Haritonov’s findings and RAMMS simulations [Харитонов, 1979; Christen et al., 2012].

For avalanche monitoring in the Kamchik Pass area, the applied techniques allowed detection of some avalanche release tracks. However, during the study period (2022-2023), avalanches were few and mostly small, making them difficult to distinguish in the SAR imagery. In some cases, avalanches reaching the road were cleared before the next acquisition, which further limited their detectability. Generated RGB composites still enabled visualization of tracks in larger avalanche catchments and provided information on snow distribution changes on the slopes using a triplet of continuous TSX–PAZ–TSX datasets acquired on 12, 16, and 23 February 2022 (ascending orbit). These methods can be extended to glaciated areas to determine locations where avalanche activity may significantly contribute to glacier mass accumulation.

In future work, we plan to combine these results with a backscatter coefficient-based analysis method developed for the Kamchik and Chimgan areas using Sentinel-1 data (2017-2023) [Семакова, Поторжинский, 2024]. This will improve detection of avalanche activity, assessment of snow distribution, snow wetness and the avalanche type by genesis over broader regions.

Conclusion. In this study, TerraSAR-X / PAZ SAR data proved effective for monitoring glacier surface changes, ice velocity, and landslide deformation in mountainous regions of Uzbekistan. Daily glacier lowering rates can contribute to future glacier mass balance estimates and provide insights into glacier dynamics. Avalanche monitoring in the Kamchik Pass area was limited by small and infrequent events during the study period. However, larger avalanche tracks in catchments where avalanches did not reach the road, as well as snow distribution changes, were successfully detected using RGB composites of coherence and intensity variations.

The results highlight the potential of high-resolution SAR datasets for operational monitoring of natural hazards in remote mountain areas. Future work will integrate these findings with Sentinel-1 analyses to enhance avalanche detection and monitoring of glacier surface deformation, providing a more robust framework for hazard mitigation and glacier mass balance studies in Uzbekistan.

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